

Energy Crests and Troughs in Quantum and Classical Waves?

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In (1) it is stated that in a two slit experiment a quantum particle goes through one slit or the other whereas for a classical wave such as sound half the wave goes through one slit and the other half through the other. This is similar to the statement of Dirac that a particle interferes with itself. (2) Nevertheless, the same two slit interference pattern ultimately applies to both. For a classical particle with a constant momentum, $x = (\text{constant velocity}) t$ and there is no notion of an interference pattern.

In previous notes (3) we argued that the relativistic and nonrelativistic classical actions $A = -m_0 t \sqrt{1-v^2}$ and $A = t \cdot \frac{1}{2} mv^2$ may be written in terms of $v = x/t$ and x and t varied independently. This leads to $dA/dx \text{ partial} = p$ and $dA/dt \text{ partial} = -E$ and suggests that $A = -Et + px$ where E, p, t and x are independent. For a classical particle, however, $x = (\text{constant velocity}) t$ and one may suggest that $p = Ev$. This is in complete contradiction to the idea of x and t being independent. We argue that there are two different relationships which are linked to A . First, $dA=0 = -E dt + p dx$ or $dx/dt = p/E$ which describes a classical wave and requires a medium. Secondly, $dA=0 = -dE t + dp x$ or $v = x/t = dp/dE$. Here one has $x/t = p/E = dp/dE = v$ constant for a free relativistic particle and the single particle is a medium.

dx/dt for $dA=0$ is different from x/t which holds for both a classical particle and the $dA=0/dp/dE=v$ scenario.. It leads to the classical wave result: $v_{\text{wave}} = f \lambda$ or E/p . When dealing with x and t i.e. dx/dt one considers a physical change in space which applies to a classical wave and requires a medium. This change describes the medium whether one has a transverse or longitudinal wave. For dp/dE which is linked to a quantum mechanical scenario one does not focus on x and t , but rather on dp and dE . One has a physical medium of a single particle and so speaks of a kind of probability. This probability must display spatial changes much like the classical wave due to an energy-momentum disturbance. This suggests a dip in probability followed by a peak (like a classical wave), but unlike the classical wave there is a single particle and so there must be a separate dimension which behaves in an opposite manner to maintain a constant probability at each x . Thus one has duality- a two dimensional wave with a single particle as its medium to indicate an energy-momentum disturbance, but at the same time invariance at each x as if one had a classical particle.

We try to investigate some of these ideas.

Motion

In classical mechanics constant motion appears as a translation in space and time of an object and its energy/mass. There seems to be no sense of action/reaction. One may, however, argue that at a certain (x,t) one has a mass (energy) and then at $(x,t+\Delta t)$ the mass (energy) has vanished. A classical mechanical particle is described by $x(t)$ and so x is associated with the center-of-mass of the particle and one does not consider a steady stream picture. Such a picture, however, with many particles each with the same velocity and some spacing would lead to a description at a fixed x_0 of: mass at t_0 - no mass at t_1 - mass at t_2 etc. Here there is no

conservation in the sense that new mass is constantly fed into the system. Mass and energy are linked together as the particle contains all of its energy $m_0/\sqrt{1-vv}$.

A classical wave (e.g. water wave or sound) shows that energy/momentum may move on its own without an accompanying mass. There is certain degree of decoupling between the two, although a medium is required. This medium does not move fully with the wave and so there must be an indication of the passing of the wave i.e. the energy affects the medium, but at the same time there must be conservation because the medium is not being created or disappearing. This leads to nonlocality because if there is a manifestation of the wave involving the increase of density at one x point, by conservation of medium, there must be a decrease at an x nearby. Both transverse and longitudinal waves follow this pattern. For sound, a longitudinal wave, density increases at the wave peak and so there is lower density behind. For a transverse wave (wave on string or water wave) there is matter above the water line for the peak and a dip behind.

This begs the question: Is it possible to have another kind of wave which has dips and peaks of a classical wave and yet does not separate the energy wave from the medium i.e. is like a classical moving particle in that respect?

Classical Action and Dispersion Relations

In a previous note (3) we argued that one may take the classical free particle relativistic or nonrelativistic action $A = -m_0 \int \sqrt{1-vv}$ or $A = \int .5mvv$, write $v=x/t$ and vary x and t independently to yield:

$$dA/dx \text{ partial} = p \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad dA/dt \text{ partial} = -E \quad ((1b))$$

From these, a solution is

$$A = -Et + px \quad ((2))$$

with E, p, t and x being independent. This differs greatly from the view of classical mechanics for which one has $x(t)$ i.e. the whole idea is that x and t are not independent. Nevertheless $((1a))$ and $((1b))$ follow directly from the classical free particle action which is associated with $x(t)$ and $p=Ev$ (for a relativistic particle) or $p=mv$ nonrelativistically.

Are there physical consequences (new solutions) to $((2))$ or is it simply a "curiosity"? We have argued in previous notes that $((2))$ gives rise (describes) both classical waves and a quantum particle with constant momentum.

Classical Wave

In the case of the classical wave one goes back to the idea of linked space and time, but does not use x/t for a classical particle, but rather dx/dt i.e.

$$dA = 0 = -E dt + p dx \rightarrow dx/dt = E/p \quad ((3))$$

Note that the dispersion relationship $dx/dt = E/p$ differs from $p=Ev$ for a classical relativistic particle. The fact that one considers changes in dx and dt means that these must be “marked” in space and time somehow. Given the different dispersion relationship from $p=Ev$, ((3)) does not seem to describe energy moving in space together with matter. Rather it seems one needs a medium (classically made of matter e.g. water or air) which is:

(A) Conserved and (B) changes in a way to indicate that energy is passing through ((4))

As a result, there is a high density followed by a low density pattern for a longitudinal sound wave or a water hump above the water line followed by a dip (below the water line) for a water wave. In both cases the medium (air or water) does not follow the wave. The classical wave is an energy disturbance with energy in a sense decoupled from the matter of the medium. This is very different from a classical mechanical particle in which the energy and matter and position and time are together. One may also note that the classical wave leads to nonlocality because due to conservation of the medium an increase in medium density or height in one place leads to a decrease slightly behind. In other words one has a physical wave. For a continuous stream of waves one would have a continuous trough-peak pattern.

Quantum Free Particle

It seems, however, that ((2)) has a second solution, namely:

$$dA = 0 = -dE t + dp x \rightarrow x/t = dE/dp \quad ((5))$$

A classical mechanical particle may be described by $x/t=v$ constant and dE/dp leads to the same form. In fact, using $E=pc+m_0c^2$ shows that:

$$dE/dp = E/p = v \quad ((6))$$

Thus ((6)) seems to be closely linked to a classical particle in that one has the same velocity as this particle (unlike the classical wave), but at the same time something different is happening because one uses dE/dp . In such a case one does not focus on x and time, but there must be a “marking” occurring. Where can this marking of the solution ((6)) occur but in time and space? For the classical wave the marking occurred in space and time i.e. a wave crest occurs at a certain (x,t) and then moves along and (x,t) changes with it. One wants x and t to be decoupled for ((6)) and so may focus on x alone. ((6)) does not describe an energy wave decoupled from a medium, the particle is the only mass object, but it must somehow mark some kind of change in x space. At the same time, all x points must be the same because one has a particle moving with a constant velocity.

It was seen with the classical wave that “marking” together with conservation of a medium leads to nonlocality i.e. the trough and peak of a wave. For ((6)) there is somehow an energy-momentum type of wave directly linked with the single particle as its medium. In such a case, instead of having a density of a medium (which is made of many particles) one has a

single particle which must then be represented by a special probability density. The reason it is “special” is that it must allow for peaks and troughs i.e. dips. A dip is a negative probability which is not considered in usual classical probability theory. Furthermore, one may not stop with a simple probabilistic trough and peak as in the classical wave. Each x point must be identical because one has a constant velocity like for a classical mechanical particle.

A solution to this dilemma seems to be introducing a second dimension because one does not have a medium like in a classical wave which may dip in one region and create a trough in the next. Instead any dip around x (e.g. a probability dip) must be “compensated” by a peak at the same x . This is not possible in one dimension, but is possible in two. For example, one may have $\cos(kx)$ starting to fall near $x=0$ while $\sin(kx)$ starts to rise). The object:

$$\cos(kx) + i \sin(kx) \quad ((7))$$

has a constant modulus of 1. Thus the idea of an energy-momentum disturbance wave leading to two dimensional space “marking” with each dimension behaving like a classical wave (but with a phase shift between dimensions) leads to a local conservation of probability at each x .

At this point one might ask why have this dual scenario? One has two shifted spatial waves in two dimensions such that their modulus yields 1 at each x suggesting a classically translating particle with constant velocity. The main feature seems to be that like a classical wave one may have interference. The classical wave deals with density or height of water and so different waves may lead to combinations of these features. The probability wave seems to be a medium wave of one particle so different energy-momentum disturbances should also add-subtract (i.e. interfere) in the same way except that now one has two dimensions. Interference of even two waves with different k breaks the modulus 1 property of ((7)) i.e. one may then have nonlocality in space associated with the real axis.

One may note that for this solution one does not consider space and time together, they are independent. Yet one still has the same velocity as a classical particle. This seems to suggest a steady stream scenario i.e. for $\exp(-iEt+px)$ one may consider all x and see a two dimensional wave (for a given t) at all x .

Physical Manifestation of the Quantum Free Particle

In the above section we discussed the duality of quantum free particle. We argued that it particle moves with $x/t = \text{velocity}$ like a classical particle, but at the same time represents the medium of an energy-momentum disturbance. This suggests crests and troughs in the probability of finding the particle in two regions near the peak. Since one does not consider x and t as linked one cannot follow a crest as it moves along like one does for a classical wave. Rather one has a kind of steady stream picture throughout all of space. Unlike the classical wave one needs two dimensions because the particle which on the one hand displays the wave-like medium of the energy-momentum disturbance which is nonlocal, must also appear as a local classical particle. Thus one has $\exp(ipx)$ with a modulus of 1 describing the particle in space and this represents a kind of probability (called the wavefunction or amplitude).

Consider the case of a two slit barrier with a free particle. The above approach represents a steady stream (mathematically) throughout all of space of the two dimensional waves. Basically

one wants to “fill” space with the $\exp(ipx)$ wave which holds for a line i.e. one dimension. If one has two slits and a point on a screen, one may draw two lines to the point, one from each slit. These probability waves interfere to create a spatial pattern. Even though a single particle may be sent through the system it seems to be the medium of the energy-momentum disturbance which follows a probabilistic pattern albeit represented by the unusual $\exp(ipx)$ probability. Thus the sum of $\exp(ip \text{ path slit 1}) + \exp(ip \text{ path slit 2})$ should apply to a single particle as well as to an entire set which ultimately creates the full two-slit interference pattern.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider the classical action $A = -Et + px$ with E, p, t and x independent for both a relativistic and nonrelativistic particle. We argue that $dA=0$ has two solutions, $dx/dt = E/p$ which describes a classical wave and $v = x/t = dp/dE$ which describes a quantum free particle. We argue that a disturbance should mark a medium. For a classical wave, there must be a medium such as a collection of particles as in a gas or water. A crest created by the disturbance leads to a following trough or dip due to conservation of medium.

For the quantum free particle, one does not link x and t , so any solution must hold throughout space. Secondly, one assumes an energy-momentum disturbance and wants it to be marked in space like the classical wave. The issue is that the single particle is the medium, so it must have a crest probability at one x point and trough (negative probability) at an x slightly behind. This leads to nonlocality, but there is only one particle, so one needs to introduce two dimensions so that the modulus $\exp(ipx)$ is 1 describes a classical particle, but at the same time one has a two-dimensional probability wave $\exp(ipx)$ marking the energy-momentum disturbance i.e. duality.

References

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